

Synthesis and characterization of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 18-membered oxazamacrocycles

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Abstract : Complexes of the type [MLCl]Cl and ZnLCl₂ (where M = Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} and L = 18-membered macrocycle containing N₂O₃ donor set) have been synthesized by template condensation of 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane with β-diketones such as 2,4-pentanedione, 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione and 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione. These have been characterized by elemental analyses, molar conductances, IR, electronic, ¹H NMR and FAB mass spectra.

Keywords : β-Diketones, 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane, macrocyclic complexes, nickel, copper, zinc.

Introduction

Due to their relevance with naturally occurring biomolecules there has been growing interest in the recent years in the study of metal complexes of synthetic oxazamacrocycles¹⁻⁴. Such complexes are used in identification of diseased and normal tissues⁵. Zinc and cadmium complexes of 18-membered N₄O₂ oxaza Schiff base macrocycles have been synthesized by Adams *et al.*⁶. Li *et al.*⁷ have synthesized Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} complexes of dioxadiazas and trioxadiazamacrocycles containing one rigid dibenzofuran unit (DBF) and *N*-(2-aminoethyl) pendant arm. Earlier, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 12-membered N₂O₂ oxazamacrocycles have been synthesized in our laboratory^{8,9}. In the present paper, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 18-membered trioxadiazamacrocycles derived from β-diketones such as 2,4-pentanedione, 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione and 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione and 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane are described.

Experimental

NiCl₂·6H₂O (Merck), CuCl₂·2H₂O (Merck) and ZnCl₂ (Merck) were of A.R. grade. 1,13-Diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane (Aldrich), 2,4-pentanedione (Aldrich), 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione (Himedia) and 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione (Himedia) were used as such. *n*-Butanol (Sisco) and DMSO were distilled before use.

Analytical methods and physical measurements : Ni, Cu and Zn were determined by standard methods. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. Molar conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in DMSO were determined by Systronics direct reading conductivity meter-304. The IR spectra (KBr) in the region 400–4000 cm⁻¹ were recorded on a Nicolet Magna-550 FT-IR spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ on a JEOL AL-300 spectrometer at 300 MHz using TMS as a reference. The FAB mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL SX 102/DA-6000 Mass spectrometer/Data System using Argon/Xenon (6 KV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas.

Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes : NiCl₂·6H₂O (4.2 mmol, 0.993 g) was dissolved in ~20 ml of *n*-butanol with stirring and 2,4-pentanedione (4.2 mmol, 0.418 g in 20 ml butanol) was added dropwise. 1,13-Diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane (4.2 mmol, 0.919 g in 20 ml butanol) was added with constant stirring. The contents were refluxed for 8 h. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried under reduced pressure. Similarly Ni^{II} complexes of other oxazamacrocycles derived from 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione and 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione and Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of oxazamacrocycles derived from 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and β-diketones such as 2,4-pentanedione, 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione and 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione were synthesized.

Results and discussion

The reactions of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} chlorides with 1,13-diamino-4,7,10-trioxatridecane and β -diketones such as 2,4-pentanedione, 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione and 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione in 1 : 1 molar ratios have resulted in the formation of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes of 18-membered oxazamacrocycles (Schemes 1 and 2).

solutions in DMSO of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of oxazamacrocycles are observed in the range 57–81 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ indicating them to be 2 : 1 electrolytes. Thus the chloride groups which are coordinated in solid state are displaced in solution by the solvent molecules. For Mn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes of the macrocycles derived from 2,9-dihydrazino derivatives of 1,10-phenanthroline, Lewis

Scheme 1. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}.

The complexes of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} are green, blue and white solids respectively. These complexes are stable at room temperature and decompose at higher temperature. These are insoluble in most of the organic solvents such as methanol, chloroform, acetonitrile and DMF but are soluble in DMSO. The characteristics and analyses of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Molar conductances : Molar conductances of $10^{-3} M$

*et al.*¹⁰ have reported the conductances in DMSO in the range 50–80 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ confirming their 2 : 1 electrolytic behaviour. Molar conductances of $10^{-3} M$ solutions of Zn^{II} complexes in DMSO are found in the range 15–22 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ indicating them to be non-electrolytes. Thus, the chloro groups are coordinated to give tetrahedral geometry as the ether oxygens do not coordinate. Lindoy *et al.*¹¹ reported tetrahedral geometry for

Scheme 2. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes of Zn^{II}.

Zn^{II} complexes of a macrocycle 1,4-diaza-8,11-dioxa-6,7 : 12,13-dibenzocyclotetradecane. Both the chloro groups and nitrogen atoms coordinate to zinc while the ether oxygen atoms remain uncoordinated.

IR spectra : The IR spectra of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes exhibit strong bands at 1550–1639 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$. Raman *et al.*¹² have reported the absorption bands at 1580–1600 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ in macrocyclic complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}. In the IR spectra of Cr^{II}, Fe^{II} and Co^{II} complexes of macrocycles derived from dihydrazide and 2,6-diacetylpyridines, Saraswat and Rana¹³ have assigned absorption bands at 1580–1640 cm⁻¹ to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$. Chandra *et al.*¹⁴ have reported the bands in the region ≈ 1620 cm⁻¹

due to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ in the Cr^{III} and Mn^{II} complexes of the macrocycles derived from benzil, 1,2-di(*o*-aminophenoxy)ethane, 1,2-di(*o*-aminophenylamino)ethane or 1,2-di(*o*-aminophenylthio)ethane. In the complexes of Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} synthesized during the present investigations, the absence of the absorption bands at 3200–3400 cm⁻¹ have been observed which confirms the condensation of CO and NH₂ groups. Adams *et al.*⁶ have reported no absorption bands corresponding to CO and NH₂ groups in Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes derived from 2,6-pyridinedicarbaldehyde and 1,5-bis-(2-aminophenoxy)-3-azapentane.

Electronic spectra : The electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complexes exhibit bands in the region 16667–16949 cm⁻¹ and

Table 1. Physical characteristics and analyses of oxazamacrocyclic complexes

Compd.	Colour	Yield (%)	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Analyses (%) :		Molar conductances ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	IR $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ (cm^{-1})	Electronic spectral bands (cm^{-1}) and assignments
				Found	Calcd.			
$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{NiCl}_2$	Green	52.0	205	14.11 (14.17)	6.72 (6.77)	55	1556	16667 ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ 27778 ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$
$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{NiCl}_2$	Green	55.4	208	12.30 (12.32)	5.75 (5.80)	57	1569	16949 ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ 26316 ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$
$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{NiCl}_2$	Green	37.0	222	10.86 (10.90)	5.06 (5.20)	60	1583	16949 ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ 26316 ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$
$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{CuCl}_2$	Blue	26.6	205	15.00 (15.17)	6.52 (6.68)	58	1579	16129 ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$
$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{CuCl}_2$	Blue	42.0	217	13.15 (13.21)	5.77 (5.82)	62	1583	16426
$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{CuCl}_2$	Blue	58.1	230	11.65 (11.70)	5.06 (5.15)	63	1539	16949
$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{ZnCl}_2$	White	58.1	222	15.44 (15.52)	6.57 (6.66)	15	1583	-
$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{ZnCl}_2$	White	50.3	230	13.41 (13.52)	5.75 (5.82)	20	1597	-
$\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{32}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{ZnCl}_2$	White	49.1	237	11.88 (11.98)	5.13 (5.14)	22	1597	-

Table 2. Chemical shifts δ (ppm) of the protons in ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra of Zn^{II} complexes of 18-membered oxazamacrocycles

Complex	Ketone moiety			Amine moiety		
	CH_3^{a}	CH_2^{b}	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_5^{\text{f}}$	CH_2^{d}	$-\text{OCH}_2$	$-\text{NCH}_2$
$[\text{Zn}\{\text{Me}_2[18]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{Cl}_2]$	0.85s	1.86m	-	Merge with CH_2^{b}	2.88t	2.60t
$[\text{Zn}\{\text{Ph}_2[18]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{Cl}_2]$	-	1.48m	7.01(b)	Merge with CH_2^{b}	2.80t	2.58t

s = singlet, t = triplet, m = multiplet, b = broad.

26316–27778 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively indicating an octahedral geometry with D_{4h} symmetry (Table 1). Lindoy *et al.*¹⁵ have reported bands in the region 10309, 16667 and 25641 cm^{-1} due to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively in the Ni^{II} complexes of N_2O_2 macrocycles. The Cu^{II} complexes show broad bands in the region 16129–16949 cm^{-1} indicating distorted octahedral geometry due to Jahn-Teller distortion. The distortion usually leads to

an elongation of two bonds giving four short and two long Cu–L distances. A band at 16400 cm^{-1} due to ligand field transitions in Cu^{II} complexes of 5,7,12,14-tetraene has been reported¹⁶.

${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra : ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra of two Zn^{II} complexes $[\text{Zn}\{\text{Me}_2[18]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{Cl}_2]$ (I) and $[\text{Zn}\{\text{Ph}_2[18]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{Cl}_2]$ (II) have been recorded. The δ ppm values of different protons are given in Table 2. In free trioxadiazine, $-\text{NCH}_2$ protons give a triplet at δ 3.10 ppm and $-\text{OCH}_2$ protons appear as a triplet at δ 2.83

ppm. In free macrocycles, though not isolated, the peaks due to -NCH₂ protons would have appeared at lower field as compared to amine. In the present complexes, the peaks due to -NCH₂ protons have been shifted to high field, δ 2.60 and 2.58 ppm in complexes I and II respectively. The peaks due to the -OCH₂ protons remain unaffected (δ 2.88 and 2.80 ppm in complexes I and II respectively) confirming that the oxygen atoms do not participate in coordination. In free 2,4-pentanedione CH₃^aCOCH₂^bCOCH₃^a, CH₃^a protons give a singlet at δ 2.14 ppm and methylene protons (CH₂^b) give a singlet at δ 3.65 ppm. In the complex (I), CH₃^a protons of the ketone moiety give rise a singlet at δ 0.85 ppm which is at high field as compared to the ketone supporting the coordination with C=N group. The methylene protons (CH₂^b) of the ketone moiety exhibit a peak at δ 1.86 ppm. The peaks due to CH₂^d protons of the amine residue merge with CH₂^b proton peak and appear as a multiplet while in free diamine, these protons (CH₂^d) appear as a pentet. The high field shifting of CH₂^b and CH₂^d protons support the coordination of metal atom with C=N groups. In free 1,3-diphenyl-1,3-propanedione C₆H₅^fCOCH₂^bCOC₆H₅^f, CH₂^b protons appear as a singlet at δ 3.54 ppm. In the complex (II), CH₂^b protons appear as a multiplet at δ 1.48 ppm. Thus the high field

shifting of these protons supports the coordination of metal with C=N groups. The aromatic protons (C₆H₅^f) appear as a multiplet at δ 7.01 ppm. Ansell *et al.*¹⁷ have reported the X-ray crystal structure of 6,7,8,13,14,15,16,17,18,19-decahydro-5H-[e,n]-8,12-diaza-1,4-dioxacyclopentadecineiodozinc(II) iodide which shows a distorted tetrahedral coordination around Zn^{II}. It has been established that both iodine atoms and both nitrogen atoms coordinate to Zn while ether oxygens remain uncoordinated.

FAB mass spectra : The FAB mass spectra of two Ni^{II} complexes [Ni{(Me)(Ph)[18]dieneN₂O₃}Cl]Cl and [Ni{Ph₂[18]dieneN₂O₃}Cl]Cl and three Cu^{II} complexes [Cu{Me₂[18]dieneN₂O₃}Cl]Cl, [Cu{(Me)(Ph)[18]dieneN₂O₃}Cl]Cl and [Cu{Ph₂[18]dieneN₂O₃}Cl]Cl have been recorded using NBX matrix. The *m/z* values and the relative abundances of various fragments are given in Table 3. Peaks at *m/z* 136, 137, 154, 280, 289 and 307 are due to the matrix. All the complexes show peaks corresponding to molecular ion [M]⁺ and free macrocycle [L]⁺ which confirm the formation of macrocyclic complexes. The fragmentation pattern of the complex [Cu{Ph₂[18]dieneN₂O₃}Cl]Cl has been discussed in detail (Scheme 3). The complex exhibits molecular ion [M]⁺ peak at *m/z* 543 (10.5%). Fragment (b) is formed due to

Table 3. *m/z* values and % relative intensities of important peaks in FAB mass spectra of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes of macrocycles

Sl. no.	Fragment	[Ni{(Me)(Ph)[18]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl]Cl	[Ni{Ph ₂ [18]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl]Cl	[Cu{Me ₂ [18]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl]Cl	[Cu{(Me)(Ph)[18]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl]Cl	[Cu{Ph ₂ [18]dieneN ₂ O ₃ }Cl]Cl
1.	[M] ⁺	476 (6.6%)	538 (6.1%)	419 (11.5%)	481 (5.3%)	543 (10.5%)
2.	[M+H] ⁺	477 (5.0%)	539 (3.5%)	420 (15.8%)	482 (3.5%)	544 (6.3%)
3.	[M-2Cl] ⁺	404 (6.6%)	468 (7.0%)	347 (19.5%)	409 (5.2%)	471 (21.0%)
4.	[L] ⁺	346 (5.2%)	408 (7.0%)	284 (4.7%)	346 (3.0%)	408 (5.2%)
5.	[L+H] ⁺	347 (5.2%)	409 (5.2%)	285 (4.7%)	347 (3.0%)	409 (5.0%)
6.	[L-CH ₃] ⁺	331 (2.6%)	-	269 (5.0%)	331 (3.0%)	-
7.	[L-2(CH ₃)] ⁺	-	-	254 (5.0%)	-	-
8.	[L-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₅] ⁺	254 (5.2%)	-	-	254 (3.0%)	-
9.	[L-C ₆ H ₅] ⁺	-	331 (11.0%)	-	-	331 (7.9%)
10.	[L-2(C ₆ H ₅)] ⁺	-	254 (21.0%)	-	-	254 (7.9%)
11.	[M-2Cl-CH ₃] ⁺	389 (7.1%)	-	332 (15.8%)	394 (5.0%)	-
12.	[M-2Cl-2(CH ₃)] ⁺	-	-	317 (26.0%)	-	-
13.	[M-2Cl-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₅] ⁺	312 (6.6%)	-	-	317 (10.5%)	-
14.	[M-2Cl-C ₆ H ₅] ⁺	-	389 (10.5%)	-	-	394 (13.2%)
15.	[M-2Cl-2(C ₆ H ₅)] ⁺	-	312 (7.0%)	-	-	317 (23.6%)

Scheme 3. Fragmentation pattern of $[\text{Cu}\{(\text{Ph}_2)[18]\text{dieneN}_2\text{O}_3\}\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$.

the loss of one chloride from molecular ion (a) and appears at m/z 506 (37%). By the loss of the another chloride, peak due to fragment (c) is observed at m/z 471 (21%). There are two possible pathways for the fragmentation of the complex.

(A) : In this pathway, the metal ion remains attached with the macrocycle framework and step by step loss of two phenyl groups from fragment (c) gives peaks at m/z 394 (13.2%) and 317 (23.6%) due to the species (d) and

(e) respectively. Loss of Ni from species (e) finally gives the species (f) at 254 (7.9%).

(B) : In this pathway, the metal ion may be lost from the macrocyclic complex in the beginning and a peak at m/z 408 (5%) appears due to the free macrocycle (g). Subsequent loss of two phenyl groups from macrocycle gives peaks at m/z 331 (7.9%) and 254 (7.9%) due to the species (h) and (f) respectively.

The spectrum of the complex $[\text{Cu}\{\text{Ph}_2[18]\text{diene-}$

Table 4. Calculations of relative abundances of molecular ion peaks [M]⁺ due to the presence of various isotopes on the basis of binomial expansion^a

Sl. no	Ion composition	<i>m/z</i>	Fractional abundances	Relative abundances (%)	Relative abundances with respect to base peak
1.	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶³ Cu ³⁵ Cl ₂	541	(0.69)(0.76) ² = 0.398	0.398	92
2.	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶⁵ Cu ³⁵ Cl ₂	543	(0.31)(0.76) = 0.18	0.432	100
3.	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶³ Cu ³⁵ Cl ³⁷ Cl	543	(0.69)(0.76)(0.24) × 2 = 0.252		
4.	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶³ Cu ³⁷ Cl ₂	545	(0.69)(0.24) ² = 0.039	0.152	35
5.	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶⁵ Cu ³⁵ Cl ³⁷ Cl	545	(0.31)(0.76)(0.24) × 2 = 0.113		
6.	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶⁵ Cu ³⁷ Cl ₂	547	(0.31)(0.24) ² = 0.018	0.018	4

Table 5. Calculations of relative abundances of various fragments due to the presence of various isotopes on the basis of binomial expansion^a

Sl. no.	Ion composition	<i>m/z</i>	Fractional abundances	Relative abundances (%)	Relative abundances with respect to base peak
A : Fragment [C₂₅H₃₂N₂O₃CuCl]					
1.	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶³ Cu ³⁵ Cl	506	(0.69)(0.76) = 0.524	0.524	100
2.	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶³ Cu ³⁷ Cl	508	(0.69)(0.24) = 0.166	0.402	77
3.	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶⁵ Cu ³⁵ Cl	508	(0.31)(0.76) = 0.236		
4.	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶⁵ Cu ³⁷ Cl	510	(0.31)(0.24) = 0.074	0.074	14
B : Fragment [C₂₅H₃₂N₂O₃Cu]					
1.	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶³ Cu	471	0.69		100
2.	C ₂₅ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶⁵ Cu	473	0.31		45
C : Fragment [C₁₉H₂₇N₂O₃Cu]					
1.	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶³ Cu	394	0.69		100
2.	C ₁₉ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶⁵ Cu	396	0.31		45
D : Fragment [C₁₃H₂₂N₂O₃Cu]					
1.	C ₁₃ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶³ Cu	317	0.69		100
2.	C ₁₃ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃ ⁶⁵ Cu	319	0.31		45

^a(a_A.^xA + b_A.^yA + c_A.^zA +)ⁿ (a_B.^xB + b_B.^yB + c_B.^zB +)^m, where a_A, b_A, c_A etc. are the fractional abundances of the isotopes ^xA, ^yA, ^zA of element A and n is the number of atoms of A present in the ion; similarly for m atoms of B and so on.

N₂O₃}Cl]Cl has been analysed on the basis of isotopic abundances of different nuclei particularly those of Cu (⁶³Cu and ⁶⁵Cu) and Cl (³⁵Cl and ³⁷Cl). Various isotopic peaks have been observed but only the most abundant isotopic peaks have been considered while discussing the fragmentation pattern. These isotopic peaks have been analyzed on the basis of theoretical calculations (Table 4). The calculations for this complex show the molecular ion isotopic peaks at *m/z* 541, 543, 545 and 547 due to different isotopes of Cu and Cl and their relative abundances are 9.6%, 10.52%, 3.7% and 0.42% respectively; the peak at *m/z* 547 is neglected due to its low abun-

dance. In the spectrum, the relative abundances of the peaks at *m/z* 541, 543 and 545 with respect to base peak are 7.9%, 10.52% and 5.1% respectively which are close to the calculated values. Similar calculations for other fragments of this complex are given in Table 5. Thus the mass spectral results strongly support the formation of macrocyclic complexes.

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